

EFFECT OF FIBER WAVINESS ON TENSILE STRENGTH OF FLAX FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Recently, fibrous composite materials such as GFRP (glass fiber-reinforced plastics) and CFRP (carbon fiber-reinforced plastics) are effectively applied for the high demand in industrial use because their advantages are light weight, high strength and corrosion resistance. However, the disposal problem after use of these materials has also surfaced as an environmental problem. To solve this problem, many researchers have tried to use plant-based natural fibers instead of artificial fibers. However, a problem of using natural fiber is fiber waviness that affects the tensile properties. Fiber waviness is the fluctuation in fiber orientation, inherent in sliver morphology of plant-based natural fibers. Therefore, the fiber orientation in a produced composite lamina is not perfectly unidirectional. The purpose of this study is thus to clarify the relation between fiber waviness and the composite's tensile strengths by identifying the degree of fiber waviness. First, the composite lamina were produced using flax sliver and biodegradable thermoplastic resin, and the fiber orientation angles were measured at fine segments on the both surfaces of the composite lamina. Next, Local Moran's I (denoted as LM- I) was carried out for quantification of the fiber waviness. Then, using an image analysis software, we calculated various area ratios by changing the range of LM- I . When the area ratio was calculated in the range of LM- $I > 0.69$ or LM- $I < -0.1$, the correlation coefficient was calculated as -0.832. It means, if the fiber orientation angles are measured and evaluated by Local Moran's I in advance, the tensile strengths can be estimated to some degree using the optimal LM- I range. We additionally predicted fracture risk areas using Tsai-Hill criterion calculated by FEM. The result was compared with Moran's I contour map. Comparison was also done for the relation between the damage areas and experimental tensile strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, there is increasing for using composite materials because high strength and low specific gravity materials are needed in many industries as aero plane and automotive for the saving energy. On the other hand, the usage and disposal of these composites, especially GFRP (glass fiber reinforced plastics), have come to present an environmental problem. Environmental issues such as these are treated internationally with considerable attention. Consequently, composite industries are seeking more environmentally friendly materials for use of their products. Increasing interest surrounds biodegradable renewable composites reinforced with natural fibers such as jute, flax, ramie, kenaf, and curaua [1-5]. These materials are often called 'green composites' [6]. Natural fibers are light and renewable. They are also an inexpensive high-specific-strength resource. The combination of interesting mechanical and physical properties together with their sustainable character has triggered activity in the development of natural fiber-reinforced composites. Recently, natural fiber-reinforced

composites are gradually being applied to industrial products such as automobile interior components using injection moulding [6], but the morphology of reinforcement in such cases is short fibers.

Long fibers are known to be more useful than short fibers to raise composites' stiffness and strength. To exploit the capabilities of long fiber slivers, Gomes et al. [5] explored the mechanical properties of green composites reinforced by slivers of curaua fiber, using three kinds of fabrication methods. In general, the slivers have a wavy shape [8], resulting in the fiber orientation fluctuation in the composites. According to the results of the paper [5], the composites' stiffness and strength were improved by reducing their fiber orientation fluctuation. Regarding the relation between such fiber waviness and mechanical properties, Hsiao and Daniel [7] developed a theoretical model of elastic constants on a unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite with fiber waviness. In this model the shape of waviness was given as a stationary wave such as sign function. Laminate stiffness including the effect of fiber waviness was also analyzed theoretically and numerically [8, 9]. In these reports also the shape of fiber waviness was given deterministically by fixing the ratio of amplitude to wavelength (denoted as waviness parameter). Tsai et al. [10] reported the stochastic effect of fiber waviness on elastic modulus of fiber-reinforced engineering thermoplastics based on composites' micromechanics (Mori & Tanaka model). They changed statistically waviness parameter by Monte-Carlo method to clarify the effect of fiber waviness on the composites' elastic constants. But, the parameter was not changed statistically in the local areas of a composite. Relation between fiber waviness and composites' strength was also reported. Allison and Evans [11] inserted a single wave in a unidirectional composite, and discussed its strength by identifying its wavy shape as a notch. Karami and Garnich [8] applied a failure criterion to a laminate in which a fiber wavy layer is included, using a finite element analysis. In these papers the fiber wavy shape was all given as a sinusoid. [12]

Ren et al. [13] reported that tensile strength of a curaua-sliver-reinforced composite depends strongly on a statistical parameter expressing the fluctuation in fiber orientation, which was quantified through the concept of one-dimensional autocorrelation between fiber orientation angles on a composite surface. Furthermore, they extended their statistical parameter to the two-dimensional case, in which two-dimensional autocorrelation coefficient (denoted as 2D-acc) was calculated as a function of two directional relative distances between two rectangular blocks of many fiber orientation segments [14]. From the contour map of average 2D-acc, it was shown that the area ratio more than 0.3 well correlated tensile strength of a flax-sliver-reinforced composite.

As mentioned in the above, composite's failure criterions have often been used for prediction of damage occurrence or fracture in fibrous composites. When the criterion is applied for sliver-reinforced composites with fiber waviness, such as composite laminates consisting of sliver-based prepregs [15], the magnitude and distribution of damages can be evaluated numerically. If the size of the prepreg becomes large, it cannot be denied that a larger defect is included. Thus, while the similarity of fiber orientation flow was discussed through the idea of autocorrelation in the previous papers [13, 14], it is variable from the viewpoint of quality control to analyze the distribution of defective areas for sliver-reinforced composites.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of the fiber waviness on the tensile strength of flax fiber-reinforced composites. First, the specimens were produced by the natural fibers and a biodegradable resin. Next, fiber orientation angles were measured, and quantified by spatial autocorrelation. Finally, we applied Tsai-Hill criteria for prediction of the damage distribution based on finite element analysis, and diagnosed the applicability for tensile strength prediction.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The specimens were performed on natural fibers as flax slivers (Teikokusen-I Co, Ltd) in fig.1 and a biodegradable resin (Randy PL-1000; Miyoshi Oil and Fat Co. Ltd., Japan) as a matrix. The resin was supplied in a water emulsion containing micro-order fine particles of approximately 5.0 μm diameter. The Randy PL-1000 is made from plant-derived resins. Some physical and mechanical properties were shown in the table 1.

Table 1 Properties of the fibers and matrix.

Material	Density (Mg/m ³)	Fiber width (μm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Fracture strain (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
Randy PL-1000	1.2	-	32.5	-	3.8
Flax fiber	1.50	10-30	600-1100	1.5-2.4	40-100

Fig.1 Flax sliver

Fig.2 A biodegradable resin

2.2 Molding process

First, the water emulsion resin was pasted on the one side of the sliver and dried for 24 hours, and next it was done on another side with the same process as the opposite side. Sliver weight before the resin pasting process was measured for the calculation of fiber content, as described later. We call the resin-pasted sliver 'pre-preg'. After such preparation, the pre-pregs were cut into the size 100 mm x 100 mm, and two pre-preg pieces were inserted into a mold in a compression molding machine. The mold temperature was set at 150°C for 40 min, and the hydraulic pressure was set at 3MPa. Subsequently the temperature was reduced to room temperature at 3MPa pressure for 24 hours.

Flax slivers were combed to form unidirectionally oriented fibers before resin pasting.

2.3 Tensile test

Obtained composite specimens were first cut to 15 mm x 50 mm, and four aluminum plates with 15 mm x 15 mm size were attached with epoxy adhesive to both ends of all specimens for tensile testing. To prevent stress concentration near the aluminum plate ends during the tensile testing, the plates were shaved to 45°. A strain gage was attached on the center of specimens to measure uniaxial strain along the tensile direction. Tensile test was carried out using an Instron-type testing machine (Autograph IS-500, Shimadzu Corp.), of which the cross-head speed was given as 1.0 mm/min. From the obtained stress-strain diagram, it was readily apparent that the composite specimens behaved almost linearly up to around 1.0% strain. Consequently, Young's modulus was calculated in the range of 0.2 – 0.5% strain for each specimen. The fiber volume fractions of all composite specimens were calculated as:

$$V_f = 1 - \frac{W - W_f}{\rho_m V} \quad (1)$$

Where, W is the composite specimen weight, W_f is the flax weight in the composite, V is the composite specimen volume, and ρ_m is the density of the biodegradable resin. The average fiber volume fractions of the composite specimens obtained here are shown in Table 2.

2.4 Angle measurement

To measure fiber orientation angles on the composite specimen's surface is quite important for calculation of stress distribution in the composite with fiber waviness. For the present angle measurement, first, x -axis was placed along the longitudinal direction of the specimen, and y -axis was placed along the transverse direction. Next, the specimen was divided into small segments of 1.0 mm x 1.0 mm square size which are composed of 50 segments along x -axis and 15 segments along y -axis. Thus, the total number of segments is 750 for each side on the specimen. The fiber orientation angle was measured for each segment. The image analysis software used was 'A-zou' of Asahi Kasei Co., Japan.

(a) Division into segment

(b) Angle θ in a segment ($\Delta x = \Delta y = 1$ mm)

Fig. 3 Measurement of fiber orientation angles on flax sliver-reinforced composites.

2.5 Finite element method

In this research, the finite element method with a 4-node isoparametric element is used for the calculation of stress distribution on the specimens. We assume that the material used here is an orthotropic property, and the stress-strain relation is given as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = [T_{ij}]^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & C_{16} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & C_{26} \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & C_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & C_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{45} & C_{55} & 0 \\ C_{16} & C_{26} & C_{36} & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} [T_{ij}] \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_z \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{zx} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where, $[T_{ij}]$ is the coordinate transform matrix. The stiffness matrix components, c_{ij} for an orthotropic material in terms of the engineering constants is shown as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11} &= \frac{1-v_{23}v_{32}}{E_2E_3\Delta}, \quad c_{22} = \frac{1-v_{13}v_{31}}{E_1E_3\Delta}, \quad c_{12} = \frac{v_{21}+v_{31}v_{23}}{E_2E_3\Delta} = \frac{v_{12}+v_{32}v_{13}}{E_1E_3\Delta}, \\ c_{13} &= \frac{v_{31}+v_{21}v_{32}}{E_2E_3\Delta} = \frac{v_{13}+v_{12}v_{23}}{E_1E_2\Delta}, \quad c_{33} = \frac{1-v_{12}v_{21}}{E_1E_2\Delta}, \quad c_{44} = G_{23}, \quad c_{55} = G_{31}, \\ c_{66} &= G_{12}, \quad \Delta = \frac{1-v_{12}v_{21}-v_{23}v_{32}-v_{31}v_{13}-2v_{21}v_{32}v_{13}}{E_1E_2E_3} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, and G is shear modulus. When Y -axis is placed as the longitudinal direction, a fiber alignment has an angle θ to Y -axis on X - Y plane, and then the stress-strain relation is to be changed as equation 4.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \tau_{23} \\ \tau_{31} \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} = [T_{ij}] \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}, \quad [T_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} m^2 & n^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2mn \\ n^2 & m^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2mn \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m & -n & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & n & m & 0 \\ -mn & mn & 0 & 0 & 0 & m^2 - n^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Where, $m=\cos\theta$, $n=\sin\theta$. The measured fiber orientation angle was substituted into θ . Elastic constants used here are as follows: E_1 and $E_3=3210$ MPa, $E_2=39500$ MPa, ν_{21} and $\nu_{13}=0.401$, ν_{12} and $\nu_{32} = E_1/E_2*\nu_{21}$, G_{12} and $G_{23}=1610$ MPa and G_{31} is assumed as being $G_{12}/2$. The boundary condition is a forced displacement, which is applied at one end of the finite element mesh along Y-axis, as shown in Fig.4. Another end is fixed along Y-axis.

Fig.4 Three-dimensional representation of finite element mesh.

2.6 Damage criterion and spatial autocorrelations

To evaluate damage area in the composites with fiber waviness, furthermore, damage risk points in the specimen were predicted using Tsai-Hill theory and spatial autocorrelation.

Tsai-Hill criterion: In this study, the stress in the direction 2 along the fiber direction, stress in the direction 1 transverse with the fiber direction and the shear stress were calculated at each element using the finite element analysis. Then, Tsai-Hill criterion was applied for definition of risky areas on the specimen. The stresses at each element are influenced by the interaction between elements. For this influence, σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} were the major stress components, so in this study Tsai-Hill criterion was reduced as the following:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{S_1}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{S_2^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{S_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

where, S_2 is the longitudinal strength, S_1 is the transverse strength, S_{12} is the shear strength. Hereinafter, Tsai-Hill criterion was denoted as TH.

Local Moran's I: Local Moran's I was created by Moran [17]. It is a typical tool of spatial autocorrelation to analyze data because it is based on a deviation from the average. The equation of Local Moran's I is shown as:

$$I(\theta_i) = \frac{(\theta_i - \bar{\theta})}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\theta_i - \bar{\theta})^2} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n w_{ij}(d) (\theta_j - \bar{\theta}) \quad (6)$$

where $w_{ij}(d)$ is the weight function of the pair samples in distance d between the pair points, i -th and j -th locations, given as:

$$w_{ij}(d) = \{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2\}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (7)$$

where x_i is i -th position of the x -axis, and the range is 1–50 mm. Also, y_i is the i -th position of the y -axis, and the range is 1–15 mm. θ_i and θ_j are the angle data at the i -th and j -th positions, respectively. Hereinafter, Local Moran's I is denoted as LM- I . LM- I varies between -1 to +1. If LM- I approaches

+1, then the angle at this location is more largely far from the average, but similar to the neighbor's angles in their deviation from the average. On the other hand, if $LM-I$ tends to approach -1, then the angle at this location is also higher or lower than the average. But, the sign is different from the neighbor angles. When $LM-I$ tends to approach 0, the angle at this location is similar to the average. Theoretically, when $LM-I$ is either much higher or lower than 0, then the fiber orientation angle is significantly different from the average. Consequently, such $LM-I$ points, if gathered locally, could form a large disordered area in fiber orientation.

Local Geary's c : Local Geary's c is another typical spatial autocorrelation to analyze a deviation from the surroundings. The equation of Local Geary's c is shown as:

$$c(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\theta_i - \bar{\theta})^2} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n w_{ij}(d) (\theta_i - \theta_j)^2 \quad (8)$$

Local Geary's c is hereinafter denoted as $LG-c$. $LG-c$ varies between 0 and 1. When $LG-c$ tends to approach 0, the angle at this location is similar to the neighbor angles. In contrast, when $LG-c$ tends to approach 1, the angle at this location differs from the sign of neighbor angles or much higher than the neighbor's angles in absolute value. Consequently, such points can be disordered parts in fiber orientation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Tensile test and analytical results

This study aims to analyze the effect of fiber waviness on the tensile strength of sliver-based natural fiber composites. The test results are shown in Table 2. The tensile strength of the direct method (DM), which consists of plenty fiber waviness, is lower than the sheet laminate method (SLM) for all specimens. Fiber waviness was quantified by the fiber orientation angles. According to Table 2, they have a wide range of positive twenty degrees to negative twenty degrees. The contour map of the fiber orientation angle distribution of specimen no.1U is shown in Fig.5. The fractured specimen is shown in Fig.6.

Contour maps of Tsai-Hill criterion based on 3D-FEM and spatial autocorrelation analyses are shown in Fig.7. Red color areas in the maps are estimated to be areas suffering damage more intensely in the specimen. The scale of the areas is clearly the largest in Fig. 7(c). It is observed that such risky areas in Figs. 7(a), 7(b) and 7(c) pass one part of the fracture path in Fig. 6

Fig.5 Contour map of fiber orientation angle distribution (Specimen no.1U)

Fig.6 Fractured specimen (Specimen no.1U)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7 Contour maps of Tsai-Hill criterion based on 3D-FEM and spatial autocorrelation analyses (Specimen no.1U) (a) Tsai-Hill distribution (b) Local Geary's c (c) Local Moran's I

3.2 Area ratio

In this research, we tried to quantify the ‘intensities’ of the Tsai-Hill criterion and spatial analyses by using the concept of ‘area ratio’. If the area ratios are well correlated with tensile strength data, the strength could be estimated from the fiber orientation angle distribution measured in advance. In this quantification, we used two imaging programs; first ‘Graph R221’ was used for plotting a contour map of the above three methods, and next ‘Azo R235’ used to calculate area ratio. Regarding Tsai-Hill criterion, the distribution varies between 0 and 1. When TH tends to approach 0, this location is not a risk point. In contrast, when TH tends to approach 1, this location is identified as a riskier point. The black areas in Fig.8 (a) consist of areas higher than 0.15 in TH values. In this example, the area ratio was 43.2%. If we choose an appropriate intensity range, the area ratio is effectively correlated with tensile strength, as mentioned later.

Table 2. Fiber orientation angles and mechanical properties of flax sliver-reinforced composites.

Production method	Specimens						Tensile strength (MPa)	Young’s modulus (GPa)
	Sample No.	Fiber volume fraction	Side A (lower angle)		Side B (higher angle)			
			Avg. angle (°)	S.D. of angles (°)	Avg. angle (°)	S.D. of angles (°)		
SLM	-	0.71	0	-	0	-	238	40.5
DM	<1>	0.55	1.99	3.54	3.30	4.28	132	22.7
	<2>	0.55	2.62	5.22	4.19	4.03	224	26.7
	<3>	0.55	5.14	4.06	5.55	3.18	158	29.6
	<4>	0.55	3.05	3.22	8.76	4.18	211	27.6
	<5>	0.65	1.74	3.73	2.85	2.66	158	23.3
	<6>	0.65	2.10	2.62	3.07	3.48	203	26.4
	<7>	0.65	1.61	2.33	2.20	2.32	153	27.5
	<8>	0.65	2.08	3.47	3.76	2.95	170	28.0
	<9>	0.65	1.45	3.72	5.26	4.77	173	26.8
	<10>	0.65	0.76	3.50	4.55	3.90	168	28.8
	Avg.	0.61	2.35	3.50	4.35	3.60	175	26.8

The number of SLM specimens was seven.

When we choose temporarily the intensity range higher than 0.65 or less than -0.15 , the black areas of LM-I is obtained, as shown in Fig. 8(b). The area ratio was 6.80% (positive side =4.80%, negative side =2.00%). The range of negative values is designated more widely than that of positive value, because the segments with negative LM-I values are not so major, but have a possibility of causing premature damage in shear. Thus, wide range negative values and relatively high positive values are corresponding to risky areas. In Fig 8(c), the black areas of LG-c are higher than 0.35 were selected. The area ratio was 12.80%. As is easily known, when the intensity ranges of TH, LM-I and LG-c are changed, the area ratios accordingly change. We consider, if appropriate intensity range(s) are given, there is an optimal area ratio at each specimen which is well correlated with tensile strength. This is because the ratio of segments suffering damage during tensile loading should be related closely with the area ratio. In the next section, thus, the relation between area ratio and tensile strength is investigated.

Fig.8(a) Binary images of Tsai-Hill criterion (Threshold level : $TH > 0.15$)

Fig.8(b) Binary images of Local Moran's I distribution (Threshold levels: positive $LM-I = 0.65$ and negative $LM-I = -0.15$)

Fig.8 (c) Binary images of Local Geary's c distribution (Threshold level: $LG-c = 0.35$)

3.3 Relation between area ratio and tensile strength

Fig. 9 shows the relation between TH's area ratio and normalized tensile strength. In this relation, the intensity range higher than 0.15 was selected. The correlation coefficient between the area ratio and the tensile strength was 0.438. The positive correlation coefficient means the tensile strength has a tendency to increase with increasing the area ratio. This is inconsistent with the concept of common fracture criteria as well as Tsai-Hill criterion. In other words, the magnitude of risky areas is directly correlated with the level of tensile strength. Fig.10 shows a case that the intensity range of $LM-I$ higher than 0.69 or less than -0.10 was chosen. The correlation coefficient between the area ratio and the tensile strength of $LM-I$ was calculated as -0.832, which is relatively high value in absolute value. It means that the level of tensile strength is roughly possible to be predicted. On the other hand, in the case of the intensity ratio of $LG-c$ in fig.11 higher than 0.50, the correlation coefficient between the area ration and the tensile strength was 0.098. This level of correlation coefficient is quite non-correlative, and thus this method cannot be used in evaluating tensile strength. The correlation coefficients between the tensile strength and area ratio were calculated for the all methods by various intensity ranges, as shown in Table 3.

Fig.9 TH area ratio dependence on normalized tensile strength

Fig.10 $LM-I$ area ratio dependence on normalized tensile strength

Fig.11 LG-*c* area ratio dependence on normalized tensile strength

5. Conclusions

The effect of the fiber waviness on tensile strength of a flax sliver-reinforced composite was investigated, using Tsai-Hill criterion, Local Moran's *I*, and Local Geary's *c*. The intensities of these parameters were quantified by use of 'area ratio'. Local Moran's *I* is well correlated with tensile strengths of the composite specimens within several intensity ranges.

Normally, finite element analysis is a well-known method for finding mechanical behaviors of composite materials, such as stress distribution. However finite element method needs to use several math models to find the solution that take time and the advanced knowledge for understanding. Thus, this study used the spatial analysis that has less equation and does not take a long time for creating the program. Finally, we conclude that the method proposed in this study is quite effective in predicting roughly the tensile strength of natural-fiber-sliver reinforced composite materials.

Table 3. Correlation between tensile strength and area ratio

Method	Intensity range	Correlation coefficient between area ratio and normalized tensile strength
Tsai-Hill criteria	TH > 0.10	0.318
	TH > 0.15	0.438
	TH > 0.20	0.399
Local Moran's <i>I</i>	LM- <i>I</i> > 0.69 or LM- <i>I</i> < -0.01	-0.682
	LM- <i>I</i> > 0.69 or LM- <i>I</i> < -0.10	-0.832
	LM- <i>I</i> > 0.69 or LM- <i>I</i> < -0.19	-0.601
Local Geary's <i>c</i>	LG- <i>c</i> > 0.2	0.113
	LG- <i>c</i> > 0.4	-0.029
	LG- <i>c</i> > 0.5	0.098

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